

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Roadmap and governance model for the HPCW
Milestone M1.2**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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Governance

The High Performance Climate and Weather Benchmark (HPCW) is a set of reference codes and an associated framework. HPCW allows a much more realistic assessment of computational performance of large HPC applications from the domain of climate research and weather forecast systems than current generic benchmarks such as HPL and HPCG.

A steering group has been implemented, consisting of the lead of the ESiWACE3 work package 1 being responsible for governance and evolution of HPCW, and of representatives of the ESiWACE3 beneficiaries which contribute to this task, namely DKRZ, BSC, ECMWF and EVIDEN.

The steering group

- monitors and guides the work on HPCW.
- will, in particular, synchronize the work between ESiWACE3 and other parties or projects contributing to HPCW.
- evaluates options for additional funding and institutional commitment.
- discusses strategies with respect to ownership, licensing, dissemination and target audience of the HPCW.

The steering group will meet quarterly.

The steering group has agreed on the following roadmap for HPCW.

Roadmap

Core set-up to be resourced by ESiWACE3, WP1

To foster and facilitate the adoption of HPCW, a subset of open-source components has been selected from the full HPCW2.0. This subset will be referred to as **HPCW-core**.

The **HPCW-core** consists of

- The **HPCW framework**
- **ecTrans**: A module developed by ECMWF for performing efficient spectral transforms of global meteorological fields in a distributed memory context. It consists of compute- and communication-heavy routines and is therefore an excellent stress-test for any machine. ecTrans.
- **CLOUDSC**: A cloud microphysics parameterization scheme developed by ECMWF. CLOUDSC is considered an archetypal physical parameterization scheme, operating on a

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globe of atmospheric columns with no horizontal dependency, and is therefore a common target for optimisation and porting efforts intended for parameterization schemes as a whole. CLOUDSC contains no communication routines and is therefore a useful test-bed for CPU or GPU-local optimisation approaches such as vectorisation.

- **ecRad**, an atmospheric radiation scheme designed for computing profiles of solar and thermal infrared irradiances

The **HPCW-core** will be implemented (or, if the codes are already running on a system, the implementation will be documented) on as many EuroHPC systems as possible, depending on their availability, access policy and the support provided by the hosting sites. To this end we will evaluate with the CASTIEL2 project and the EuroHPC JU to what extent the **HPCW-core** can be included in the common CI/CD environment. We will insist, however, that the **HPCW framework** is used for deployment, profiling and documentation of components.

Documentation of **HPCW-core**, its results and instructions on its deployment as well as information on related activities outside of ESiWACE3 will be published on the ESiWACE3 website.

Extended set-up to be resourced from external funding sources

Within the EuroHPC JU-funded project HANAMI, which is expected to start in the first quarter of 2024, we plan to consolidate the ICON benchmark, which is part of the HPCW2.0, and make it available under an open-source licence.

Also, within HANAMI, a kernel based on the Japanese NICAM model of the atmosphere will be deployed on a number of EuroHPC JU systems using the **HPCW framework**.

Further, it is planned to deploy the **HPCW-core** and the ICON benchmark on at least one HPC system (Fugaku) in Japan.

The NEMO ocean model is used for co-design in central European projects such as EPI. We are looking for ways to maintain NEMO as part of HPCW, even if there is currently no explicit funding available for this.

These activities and their results, which we envision to form an **extended core of HPCW**, will also be documented on the HPCW pages on the ESiWACE3 website.

Legacy HPCW codes

For some of the benchmarks that were included in the previous versions of HPCW there are currently no concrete plans for further development:

- IFS-RAPS has a restricted licence model and cannot be freely distributed. However it will be used within HANAMI and being a benchmark with a long history and a complete model including all representative motives of a weather codes it may be kept as reference within HPCW
- The implementation of the IFS-FVM dwarf depends on tools developed by Swiss institutions and thus cannot be supported by EuroHPC JU funded activities.

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- The KRONOS workload simulator and the ACRAEB2 radiation code will no longer be considered for HPCW in the future as we need to restrict the number of codes and want to concentrate on open-source codes.